

Strategic and Comprehensive: Modeling MOOC Learner Behavior through Process Mining of Learning Sequences

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Abstract. This exploratory study analyzes student behavior in a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). MOOCs represent a global educational phenomenon transforming teaching and inspiring new research perspectives on learning methods in higher education institutions. Understanding how students organize their learning sequences and how these relate to their academic performance is crucial for optimizing digital educational processes. The objective of this study is to identify and characterize the learning sequences performed by students during their study sessions in a MOOC, using process mining (PM) techniques. The methodology involved analyzing a dataset collected between July 2017 and January 2018, comprising 27,922 students and approximately 3.5 million recorded interactions. Process mining techniques were employed to examine these learning sequences. Results indicate that most interactions correspond to assessments and video lectures, while forums were the least utilized activity. Additionally, two student profiles were identified: "Comprehensive" learners, who follow expected sequences and engage in longer, more intensive study sessions, and "Strategic" learners, who prioritize assessments. This study advances the current understanding of online learning and situates its findings within the broader literature by contrasting them with similar classification patterns reported by other authors.

Keywords: Learning Analytics, Process Mining, Learning Behavior, Massive Open Online Course.

1 Introduction

MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) are a global phenomenon that is transforming teaching and making researchers reflect on new ways of learning in higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide. The increase in the interest and importance of MOOCs is reflected in the increase in the number of students registered for courses and in the number of courses published. As of February 2024, nearly 440 million students were reported to have registered in one of the more than 29.5 thousand MOOCs published according to Class Central [1]. This accelerated growth and its rapid adoption in different countries has caught the attention of researchers, who seek to understand how it has spread, its characteristics, the impact on students, but also seek to understand the low pass rates that are only around 5% in this type of course [2]. While initial research

on MOOCs focused on understanding completion rates and final course grades, more recent work has examined how students move through course content as a way to understand the learning process itself [3]. In this way, thanks to the fact that MOOC platforms record the clicks of students' interactions with resources, it is possible to investigate their behavior.

The analysis of the detailed interactions with the learning activities such as video lectures, evaluations, readings, forums, etc., have allowed us to understand the degree of commitment that a student establishes with the course resources (for example, micro-interactions) [4]. However, little is known about the learning sequences that students take when interacting with course activities. In addition, little is known about the itineraries that students take during their study sessions, and how they distribute study sessions in relation to their length and frequency throughout the course. However, the research developed to obtain models of student behavior based on data provided by Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Learning Management Systems have revealed information on how students engage and interact with different learning activities [5], [6]. More research is needed to advance the understanding of the learning paths that students consider in the course in order to achieve their goals.

The aim of this article is to address these gaps in the literature and using Process Mining (PM) techniques to explore the behavior of students in a MOOC during their study sessions, analyzing the learning sequences that occur both at the macro (weekly/topical) and micro levels (interactions with MOOC resources). This will contribute to the understanding of how students in an online environment manage their study sessions through a MOOC and its relationship with academic achievement. The article is structured as follows: section 2 presents the related work and research questions that serve as the basis for conducting this study, section 3 presents the methodological approach used to answer the research questions, section 4 presents the main results, section 5 presents the discussion of these results, and finally section 6 presents the main conclusions and limitations of the study.

2 Related Work

2.1 Patterns of MOOC behavior

In online learning, as well as in other types of learning, student participation is considered a prerequisite for learning [7]. In a MOOC, this is the most used indicator to measure learning outcomes. Student engagement can take many forms [8]. In a MOOC, given the openness of the course, the student participates at several levels, where he or she establishes different levels of commitment to the course activities [9], [10]. For example, Xiong and colleagues [11] They found that the level of engagement in learning could be measured by the number of video lectures viewed, the number of forum posts, the number of tests taken, and the number of tasks completed. In another study, Kizilcec and colleagues [12], Based on the number of student interactions with video lectures and assessments, they ranked students based on their participation in the MOOC, where they identified four patterns of participation: 1) Explorers – those who only explore the course, 2) Watchers – who only watch video lectures, 3) Desisters –

those who drop out of the course as time goes on, and 4) Completers – those who complete the entire course. However, in a MOOC, each student sets their own goals with the course and commits in different ways. In a recent study by Maldonado-Mahauad and colleagues [3, 13, 14] it was found that the students of three MOOCs, regardless of the topic of the course, established their own objectives and participated selectively with the course contents. In this research, students were classified according to their interactions with the course activities as: 1) explorers, 2) strategic, and 3) engaged. But in addition, for each type of student, research was carried out on the learning sequences they undertook.

2.2 MOOC Learning Sessions

Recent research has shown that study sessions are still the approach used by students to organize their learning in an online context [16]. A study session can be defined as a period of time during which the student interacts with course resources and where the student's inactivity intervals in the course are no longer than 30 minutes [17], [18]. According to Tough [19], A session is defined as a period of time spent on a sequence of similar or related activities that are not interrupted by other types of activities. However, in areas such as Learning Analytics and Data Mining, studies have recently begun to be found in which the study session is considered as the unit of analysis. For example, authors such as [3], [20] using Learning Analytics they identified the learning strategies that students use in a study session for both a hybrid and online context. As a result in these studies, students were classified based on the identified strategies, resulting in a characterization of students for the online context in "Samplers", "Comprehensive", and "Targeting" students; as well as for the hybrid context in "intensive", "strategic", "highly strategic", "selective" and "highly selective" students [3], [20]. In these works, the authors have used the instructional design of the course to try to relate and interpret the patterns found. That is, they have tried to connect the design of the course with the Learning Analytics obtained. However, there is still a lack of works that consider the analysis of study sessions with different levels of granularity of the data (macro, meso, micro) and with different levels of activities in which the course is structured (activities, weeks, modules).

Based on the above, this paper proposes an exploratory study that allows: 1) to extract the learning sequences that students make when interacting with the course activities; 2) understand how students organize the different learning sequences during their study sessions in a MOOC; and 3) understand how their behavior relates to their academic performance. The research questions that this study seeks to answer specifically are:

R.Q.1. What learning sequences do students take during their study sessions in a MOOC?

R.Q.2. How can students be classified based on the learning sequences detected during a study session?

3 Methodology

This section presents the development of the exploratory study that has been carried out in the context of the Python MOOC, and with the aim of answering the research questions posed. The following sections describe the structure of the course and the characteristics of the participants in the study. The method used to extract the behavior patterns of the students is then presented.

3.1 MOOC and Participants

This exploratory study was conducted with a dataset recorded between July 2017 and January 2018. The course is structured in 6 modules. Each module is made up of a set of lessons. Each lesson is made up of a set of video lectures, theoretical and practical questionnaires and readings. In total, the course has 35 video lectures (VL), 11 readings (L), 13 practical questionnaires (QP) and 11 theoretical questionnaires (QT). All modules were available during the 6 weeks that the course lasted. Fig. 1 shows how distributed the different contents through the different lessons in each of the modules. In the course, 38,838 ($N = 38,838$) students were registered, of which 10,916 did not register any type of activity on the course.

WEEK 1	RESOURCES
Topic 1	VL VL VL VL VL VL L QT QP
Topic 2	VL VL
Topic 3	L QT
WEEK 2	
Topic 1	VL VL VL VL
Topic 2	VL VL QT
Topic 3	QP L QP L
WEEK 3	
Topic 1	VL VL VL QT
Topic 2	VL VL QT
Topic 3	QP L QP
WEEK 4	
Topic 1	VL VL VL QT
Topic 2	VL VL VL QT
Topic 3	QP L QP L QP L QP
WEEK 5	
Topic 1	VL VL VL QT
Topic 2	VL VL VL QT
Topic 3	QT L QP L QP
WEEK 6	
Topic 1	VL VL VL VL QT
Topic 2	QP L QP

Fig. 1: MOOC structure week by week

For the analysis, all students were considered, except those who did not report any activity, leaving a cohort of 27,922 students who registered about 3.5 million interactions in the course. 15% of registered students were between 18 and 24 years old, 50% were between 25 and 34 years old, and 22% were between 35 and 44 years old. 64% of the students reported being male and 34% female. 34% of the students come from Chile, 20% from Mexico, 13% from Peru, 12% from Colombia, 7% from Spain and 5% from Ecuador.

3.2 Behavioral Pattern Exploration

To explore the behavior patterns of students in the MOOC and answer the research questions, we use the Process Mining methodology called PM² [21]. PM² is a simplification and flexibility of the L* Life-cycle model [22] and it has been used in different disciplines such as health and business [23], [24]. The stages resulting from this adaptation are the following: 1) Extraction, 2) Generation of the Event Log, 3) Model Discovery, and 4) Model Analysis.

Extraction Stage. In this stage, the activity data or log files recorded by the platform were extracted. The platform generates a set of files in CSV format. This set of files consists of 86 files of which only 8 were selected (Users, Course grades, Course progress, Course items, Course item grades, Course item types, Course lesson, and Course module) to analyze student behavior based on student interactions with course resources. After this, a cleaning and transformation of the data was done.

Generation of the Event Log. In this stage, the event log is defined that will serve in the following stages to discover the process model that allows interpreting the behavior of students in the MOOC. The event log is a file that stores information about students' interactions with the digital resources of the course. The first step in generating the event log was to define two concepts to interpret the data traces of the interactions with the MOOC. Specifically, the concept of session and interaction were defined: *(1) A study session* is a period in which students interact with course resources and record continuous activity, with intervals of inactivity no longer than 30 minutes. It means; that if the student did not carry out any activity or interaction with the course, the platform will end the session and consider it as a new one [36]. *(2) An interaction* is an action that is stored in the data traces recorded by Coursera and that reflects a student's interaction with one of the MOOC's digital resources. For this work, 8 types of interactions that the student can register when interacting with video-lectures, assessments, and readings were defined. Table 1 presents the interactions and their meanings.

Table 1. Types of interaction

Resource	Interaction	Meaning
Video-lecture	VL-Begin	Video-lecture starts
	VL-Beginagain	Restart a video lecture that has not been completed
	VL-End	Complete a video-lecture
	VL-Repeat	Return to a video-lecture that you have already completed in the past to review part or all of it
Assessment	Eval-Begin	Assessment starts
	Eval-Beginagain	Restart an assessment that has not been completed
	Eval-End	Pass an assessment
	Eval-Repeat	Return to an assessment that you have already passed in the past to review part or all of it

Reading Sup Enter reading material
 The resulting event log contains: (1) user id, (2) time stamp, (3) the interaction performed, (4) the session number in which the interaction with the MOOC resources occurs (Fig 2).

	case_id	time-stamp	Actividad	Sesión	Estado
0	00032063f5c9d360e410e65732ead778cf5f64f2	2018-08-14 13:51:21.130	Video-Lectura	1	VL-Inicia
1	00032063f5c9d360e410e65732ead778cf5f64f2	2018-08-14 13:58:59.657	Video-Lectura	1	VL-Termina
2	00032063f5c9d360e410e65732ead778cf5f64f2	2018-08-14 13:59:16.640	Video-Lectura	1	VL-Inicia
3	00032063f5c9d360e410e65732ead778cf5f64f2	2018-08-14 14:02:58.905	Video-Lectura	1	VL-Termina

Fig. 2: Event log Example

Model Discovery: In this stage, a Process Mining discovery algorithm is applied. This algorithm allows us to extract a process model that models the behavior of students graphically. Specifically, the Disco software is used,¹ which implements a fuzzy algorithm (based on Fuzzy miner) [26].

Model Analysis: As a result of the previous stage, a process model is obtained for each Event Log as shown in Fig. 3. This model represents the behavior of students who do only video-lectures in the MOOC. Each box represents the activity carried out and the number inside it represents the number of times that activity is repeated by the students in the MOOC. The darkest blue box represents the activity that has been done the most times by students in the MOOC, in this case the activity "Video-lecture-Begin" has been done 7,678 times. On the other hand, the bows or arrows that join two activities (boxes) represent the transitions from one activity to another and the number above the bow represents the number of times they went from an activity "A" to an activity "B". For example, there is a path that goes from "Video-Lecture-Begin" to "Video-Lecture-End" and that path was performed 5,107 times. The highlighted black arrow represents the frequency of the transition from one activity to another and is proportional to the width of the activity.

Fig. 3: Event log Example

¹ Disco Software: <https://fluxicon.com/disco/>

4 Results

This section presents the results obtained from the analysis of the Event Logs. The results have been organized according to the research questions.

R.Q.1. What learning sequences do students take during their study sessions in a MOOC?

Based on the defined Event Log (Fig. 2), we generated the process model that contains the learning sequences of the students in the MOOC. Fig. 4 shows the process model that contains the learning sequences that students carry out in the MOOC.

Fig. 4: Process model with the learning sequences that students carry out in the MOOC

From Fig. 4 it can be seen that: 1) the activity that is repeated the most times is "Eval-Start-Again" with 2,580,932 repetitions (representing 71.43% of the total repetitions) and the transition from this activity to it repeats 2,449,399 times, this being the most

frequent activity and transition. This means that students repeatedly initiate an evaluation; 2) the next most frequent learning sequence is "VL-Begin→VL-End" repeating 159,948 times followed by the learning sequence "VL-End→VL-Begin" which is repeated 140,847 times. This means that students start and finish the video lectures proposed in the MOOC; 3) the learning sequence "VL-End→Sup→Eval-Begin→Eval-Beginagain→Eval-Beginagain → Eval-End→ Eval-Repeat→VL-Begin" is the most frequent route that students take and that adheres to the design of the MOOC. However, the sequence "Eval-End→ Eval-Repeat →VL-Begin" indicates that students after finishing an assessment return to watch it in order to monitor their progress and then prepare to start a new video-lecture. Fig. 5 presents the list of the 57,238 types of learning sessions (Variants) that the students undertook. Specifically, Fig. 5 shows session type 9 (Variant 9) in which the sequence of activities that a student performs in the MOOC in that type of session is graphically shown. This is starting and ending video lectures in the same session, where 1,728 student sessions have this type of behavior (5 events with a duration of 12 minutes).

Fig. 5: List of the 57,238 types of learning sessions in the MOOC

R.Q.2. How can students be classified based on the learning sequences detected during a study session?

To group the students, the sequences of activities that the students perform in their study sessions in the MOOC were considered (see Fig. 5 - Variants). Additionally, the frequencies of interaction of the students with: 1) formative assessments, 2) summative assessments, 3) supplements, 4) Forum, 5) Video-lecture, 6) the duration of the sessions

5 Discussion of the results

To move beyond binary categorizations (completers vs. non-completers) and develop specific interventions or adaptive features, researchers [9, 10, 12, 15] began to develop classification schemes or typologies based on student behavior and engagement patterns. These classifications help to deconstruct the broad category of ‘non-completers’ and to understand the varied ways in which students interact with MOOC platforms and content. Through these works, common archetypes emerge, particularly those representing minimal engagement (“Sampling,” “Observers,” “Samplers,” “Bystanders”) and full engagement/completion (“Completing,” “Active Participants,” “Keen Completers,” “All-rounders”). However, there is significant divergence in how intermediate levels of engagement are categorized. This variation is strongly influenced by the MOOC’s pedagogical model (xMOOC vs. cMOOC vs. socioconstructivist) and the specific data analyzed (assessment/video logs, discussion activity, qualitative interviews, specific activity types). The differences between classifications derived from Coursera [4], cMOOCs [20], and FutureLearn [17] underscore the profound impact of pedagogical choices and platform design on student behavior patterns. Social features, networking expectations, and the structure of activities shape how students interact and, consequently, how they are classified.

While prior typologies have provided essential insights into the heterogeneity of learner behaviors in MOOCs—moving beyond binary metrics such as course completion—their methodological limitations constrain the depth and actionability of the resulting analyses. Studies based on clustering techniques (e.g., [12, 28]) rely on aggregated behavioral vectors, often losing the granularity and temporality of sequential actions. Other qualitative approaches, such as observational synthesis or thematic analysis of interviews [29], provide valuable contextual depth but lack scalability and objective event-driven traceability. Furthermore, classifications based solely on activity types [30] omit the sequencing of actions, a critical dimension for understanding learning flows. In contrast, our adoption of Educational Process Mining addresses these limitations by modeling complete behavioral trajectories across different resource types, capturing both the order and timing of student interactions. This allows not only for the visualization of learning pathways and the identification of bottlenecks, but also for the systematic evaluation of alignment with instructional designs and performance outcomes. As such, our approach offers a more holistic and data-driven lens for understanding engagement in MOOCs, bridging the gap between descriptive categorization and actionable learning process diagnostics.

A relevant line of research that relates to our work is presented by Mair [27], who analyzed behavioral patterns in quiz attempts within a mandatory MOOC in Austria. In their study, the authors classified learners based on the number of quiz attempts, identifying five distinct behavioral patterns (e.g., “10 points are enough”, “training is more important than the score”, “minimal effort”, among others). Their approach focused exclusively on quiz repetitions as a proxy for engagement and learning strategies, using quantitative descriptive analysis supported by sequential visualizations. In contrast, our study adopts a Process Mining methodology, which enables us to capture and represent not only repetition patterns in assessments but also

complete temporal learning sequences across multiple types of MOOC resources (video lectures, readings, formative and summative assessments). Unlike the approach by [27], our analysis covers full learning sessions and defines learning pathways at different levels of granularity (micro, meso, and macro), offering a more comprehensive view of student behavior throughout the course. Furthermore, while [27] focused on a mandatory MOOC with a relatively small cohort ($N=1,200$), our study analyzes a large-scale open MOOC with a significantly larger cohort ($N\approx 28,000$ active students, over 3.5 million interactions), enabling broader generalization of findings to diverse learning contexts. It is worth noting that although both studies identify types of students with strategic or thorough behaviors, our approach allows us to connect these strategies with the duration and frequency of study sessions and students' final performance, as well as their engagement over time. For example, we found that strategic learners tend to have shorter sessions focused on assessments, whereas comprehensive learners spend more time and follow sequences aligned with the course's instructional design. This extends the contributions of studies like [27] by showing how navigation strategies impact the overall learning experience beyond quiz outcomes. Finally, we believe that integrating techniques such as Educational Process Mining could complement future studies on quiz behavior, like that of Mair [27], by enhancing the clarity and interpretability of analyses related to student learning behaviors in massive online learning environments.

6 Conclusions and limitations of the study

This paper presents an exploratory study to characterize student behavior in online environments. This article contributes to the study and understanding of how students develop their learning sequences in their study sessions in a MOOC. Although there is previous work in the literature that has explored the learning trajectories that students make in a MOOC [3], [13], this work, in comparison with those mentioned above, analyzes the study trajectories that students make at the micro level, as a result of interactions with the course resources. In addition, it characterizes the students' study sessions throughout the 6 weeks of the course. This allows for advanced knowledge about how students use a MOOC, whether they take it to learn by working exhaustively with course resources, or whether it is to obtain a certificate or validate their knowledge by working solely with course assessments.

The main conclusions of this study are the following. *First*, the greatest number of interactions throughout the 6 weeks occurs with summative assessments followed by video lectures. Students interact more with formative assessments than with course readings (supplements), with forums being the activity that records the fewest interactions throughout the 6 weeks. *Second*, the students, based on their learning sequences, were classified into two groups: 1) students characterized as "Comprehensive" [3], perform sequences of activities that students would be expected to perform in the MOOC. This is to work sequentially first with the Video-lectures, then the supplements as proposed in the course design. Then they address the evaluation activities and finish them before starting a new Video-lecture again; 2) students

characterized as "Strategic" [3], work exclusively with evaluations and to a lesser extent with Video lectures. These students are interested in working and passing the evaluations. These students attempt to certify the course without reviewing supplementary materials such as Video-lectures, supplements, or forums. *Third*, "Understanding" students who pass the course work sessions that on average last longer during the 6 weeks of the course compared to students in this same group who fail the course. "Understanding" students work constantly and intensively with course materials. *Fourth*, "Strategic" students who pass the course work sessions that on average last longer during the 6 weeks of the course compared to the same students in this group who fail the course. However, they work less intensely than the "Understanding" students who pass the course. This suggests that "Strategic" and course-passing students seek to certify the MOOC with no intention of working along the course route but rather focus on passing assessments.

The results of this study are subject to some limitations given by the nature of the data and the methodological choices made. First, the identification of the activities that are designed in a MOOC are limited by the technological platforms on which the courses are implemented and the interpretation of the observed actions that students perform when interacting with the course, by the quantity and quality of data that the platforms store. Second, the generalization of these results is subject to the limitations of the methodology used in this study, as well as the results obtained through the use of Process Mining techniques. Despite the aforementioned limitations, the article advances in the understanding of online learning. The findings complement previous work in the literature on other platforms for online courses such as Learning Management Systems. However, in a MOOC, students are heterogeneous and highly diverse, so the results found in this study enrich the current literature.

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